

Translating early capitalism: Cameralism, Mining and the Struggle for a Good Science of Things.

by

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Abstract:

From Melchior von Osse (1506-1557) to Johann Heinrich Gottlob von Justi (1720-1771), the cameralists have been characterised by a steady and explicit struggle for their credibility. Through the example of the Saxon mining districts and their capitalist transformation in the 15th and 16th centuries, this article illustrates two particular challenges that these princely advisors found themselves confronted with. The thesis is that the simultaneous emergence of highly differentiated economic landscapes and multilayered bureaucratic structures made the cameralist profession both necessary and prone to fail. The Prince's growing and convoluted domestic economy demanded authors who attempted to restore or at least simulate clarity and central controllability. However, the complexity of economy and administration had become far too great to be mastered and understood by single individuals. In this sense, the history of cameralism is not without tragedy. The world that demanded these authors was also a world that could no longer be translated into the unity of a book.

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1. God and the truth

Melchior von Osse (1506 – 1557), one of the first cameralists (Dittrich 1974: 41; Small 1909: 2; Zielenziger 1914: 157), was expecting that his major treatise, the so called *Testament* (pub. 1556), would attract much resistance within its audience. There would be “*evil men*”, he predicts in his dedication to August, Elector of Saxony (1526 – 1586) who had commissioned the book in August 1552, who would try and deliberately discredit some of his ideas in front of the Wettin prince. Although only “*god and the truth*” served both as his guidance and ultimate goal in compiling this volume, the majority people affected by his advices, he argues pessimistically, would most likely reject them as “*unnecessary, futile and useless*” (Osse 1717: 9-13).¹

Similar pessimistic outlooks are a characteristic feature of cameralist literature over the following centuries. Georg Obrecht (1547-1612), besides von Osse another representative of the few ‘early cameralists’ (Dittrich 1974), seems to have met strong resistance after the publication of his first treatise called *Politisch Bedencken vnd Discurs* (Obrecht 1617), which animated him to write *apologias* (e.g. in his forth treatise *Ein sondere Polickey Ordnung/ und Constitution*) in which he defended some of his ideas. The same applies for Georg Engelhard Löhneysen (1552-1622), cameralist and mining official, who railed in the preface of his *Aulico Politica* against the many “*despicable judgements*” he expected in reaction to his book and its revelation of “*foundation[s] of truth*” (Löhneysen 1622). The most important cameralist of the 17th century, Johann Joachim Becher (1635 – 1682), would later use several pages to grumble in his *Politischer Discours* (Becher 1668) about all the “*Ehrenabschneider*” who would publicly truncate his honor by doubting his knowledge and skills, even calling him a liar or a quack. His student, brother-in-law and colleague Philipp Wilhelm von Hörnigk (1640-1714), another key-figure of the cameralist discourse, would later invest two chapters of his main opus *Oesterreich uber alles, wann es nur will* to refute a series of expected criticisms. Some people would call persons like him a “*squaller and preacher of commerce,*” accusing him not only of serving primarily the fiscal interests of the emperor, but also of being naive and inexperienced in practice, lost in abstract theories, bungling project after project, leaving the people nothing behind “*but an empty cup*” (Hörnigk 1684: 14).²

¹ The reference to potentially sinister and evil men in the environment of the prince can already be found at the beginning of Melchior von Osse’s career; for example in his private correspondence with Johann Friedrich of Saxony (cf. Hecker 1922: 11).

² If not other indicated all quotations of German works were translated by the author of the article.

This list could be extended *ad libitum* and it comprises the whole spectrum of cameralist writers: officials at court as well as roaming intellectuals in search for princely funding, counsellors and practitioners as well as academics and devotees to theory. In the 18th century however, the final phase of cameralism and the era of its great systematics, this discourse seems to shift slightly. Parallel with the growing formalisation of the sciences a depersonalisation of the debates above took place. Rather than defending one's own position as a carrier of knowledge, cameralists were now occupied with the task of defending their science as valuable and necessary for society. The underlying problem had remained the same – only the borderlines were now running along disciplinary rather than individual distinctions. Still, there were many, for example in the administrative apparatuses of German territories, which dismissed the cameral sciences as a waste of time, as being impractical, too theoretical and eventually useless for the government (Wakefield 2005: 313). Moreover, there still existed many adherents of the traditional narrative of cameralists being thieves and rubbers of the public, creatures of greedy princes (Wakefield 2009: 5-10; Bauer 1997: 211; Richarz 1991: 192). Johann Georg Krünitz (1728-1796), Johann Heinrich Gottlob von Justi (1720-1771) and many colleagues therefore invested considerable intellectual resources to convince their environment that at least “good cameralists”, well-educated scholars driven only by selfless dedication to the happiness of the nation, constituted a necessary and beneficent element within society, the aristocratic courts and academia (Wakefield 2009: 5; Wakefield 2005: 312-313).

There have been many discussions over the last decades about the definition of cameralism. Von Osse, Obrecht and others did not call themselves cameralists. The term, a reference to the so-called *Kammer*, a newly established body at the early-modern courts in order to administer and improve the princely finances, only appeared around the 17th and 18th century in mostly pejorative contexts. The “*Kameraliste*” then predominantly served as a cipher or a hypernym to address individuals who worked for the chamber and who were under suspicion of enriching (themselves and/or) the prince at the people's expense (Wakefield 2009: 5; Keller 2017: 26). Recent works reflecting the relationship of cameralism and mining have in particular focused on the 18th century and the establishment of the first mining academies (Klein 2010; Schleiff, Hartmut and Konečný 2013; Konečný 2017; Felten 2019). The type of cameralist that appears in the context of these emerging institutions however tends to differ strongly from the authors mentioned above. Daniel Gottfried Schreber (1708-1777), Carl Friedrich Zimmermann (1713-1747), Carl Abraham Gerhard (1738-1821) and others could in fact be described as early manifestations of a new scientific era, the end of the old cameralist cosmos (cf. Chapter 6). Their scientific interest and expertise was comparatively narrow, dealing for example with questions of technology, mineralogy, geology or chemistry that were important in order to make

mining operations more successful. This article will instead focus on a group of texts between the 16th and 18th century that was characterized by a comparatively holistic approach concerning the science of the chamber.³ Their authors intended to win the prince's attention and benevolence by addressing as many problems of his household as possible. Therefore, they had to deal with natural philosophy, alchemy, agriculture, forestry, fishing and mining as well as with questions of tariffs and taxation, legislation, society, politics or pedagogy (Seppel 2017: 7; Reinert 2011: 237). The reasons for this inclusive approach were manifold. Cameralist oeuvres of this sort owed themselves not only to the (symbolic) economy of the courts or the logics of early-modern state-administration, but also to an array of ideological premises. Especially the politico-economic image of the state as a large household governed by a wise patriarch ("*Hausvater*") (Seppel 2017: 5; Simon 2004: 452-462; Tribe 1997: 269; Reinert 2011: 235), which combined antique economic concepts (*oikos/oikonomia*) with political ideals of personalized and monarchic rule, was of great importance here. According to a common cameralist conception, the state could be understood as "*a magnified family with a big farm as its property*" (Small 1909: 588), a house of houses, with the prince as patriarch, head of the domestic economy (both private and public) and symbol of territorial unity (Tribe 1988: 21; Burkhardt 1990: 173).

There is however, even for this chosen subset of cameralist thinkers, hardly any academic consensus beyond this rather loose collection of traits. Against this backdrop it was particularly the economic historian Lars Magnusson who was one of the first scholars who successfully introduced a discourse-analytic standpoint in this matter, emphasizing that the term (mercantilism and) cameralism seems to imply first and foremost a common language and rhetoric (Magnusson 2015: 9; Magnusson 1994; Simon 2014: 65). Seen from this perspective, the debates and conflicts relating to a certain field of expertise and knowledge could also be regarded as potential material to investigate the characteristics of its underlying scholarly practice. The starting point of the following article is hence the observation, that the history of the cameralist discourse had been accompanied by *an extraordinary intense struggle for credibility that was made explicit within the texts themselves*; a struggle which would later on, and even after its demise as an active intellectual culture, live on in the works of modern economists and economic historians in the shape of latent skepticism and ridicule. To put it differently, from the moment cameralists entered the stage of history, they found themselves confronted with rather existential forms of critique that long exceeded mere objective debates about the value of certain

³ It is important to note that cameralist thought was not merely a phenomenon within German territories. Cameralist traditions can for example also be found in Sweden, Italy, Denmark, Spain and Portugal (cf. Rössner 2017: 246).

(scientific) arguments⁴ – regardless of their respective personal background and professional career.⁵ The following pages will present the thesis that this characteristic struggle of the cameralists arose out of specific historic constellations that both created the role of the cameralist while at the same time making it impossible for them to keep up with their promises. Focusing on the example of Melchior von Osse in 16th century Saxony and its impressive mining industry, we will be able to observe how the growing complexity within economic and bureaucratic processes led to ever-larger distances and hence control issues between the Wettin princes and their subjects as well as the resources of their territory. At first, in the upcoming second chapter, this article will present a short introduction into the relationship of cameralism and mining in general. The third chapter will then demonstrate how capitalist influences transformed and enlarged the mining business in the Saxon Erzgebirge, eventually creating a *deep* and complex space of montane practices, techniques and knowledge that was hardly comprehensible for single individuals (whether prince or cameralist). To make things even more difficult for Saxon rulers or consultants a complementary process would evolve alongside the above mentioned economic dynamics: the emergence of, as the fourth chapter will argue, a *deep* space of government, of mining administration and bureaucratic regimes. This did not only add dramatically to the issue of lacking in- and oversight from both sovereign and cameralist, but also created a well informed potential enemy of cameralist credibility at court. The originally Xenophontian proverb, “*the eye of the master makes the horse fat*” (cp. Fig. 5), formed a recurring *topos* within early modern economic literature. The cameralists however, designated to moderate and close the gap between the ‘master’ and its object, were condemned to walk a fine line between expertise and ridicule as their resources were too scarce to explore the depths of economy and government as well as to translate them into the, as chapter five argues, dangerously limited space of a book. From the late 15th until the late 16th century, a period in which among others the *Testament* was published, the Saxon territorial state would increasingly inflate and overcharge the old “*oikonomia*” by becoming a “household” that was far too large to be governed and overseen by a single person. No individual, no scholar, no

⁴ An analogue rhetoric, for example in 16th century Saxony is, except for alchemical works, rare to find. It neither appears in the works of mining experts like Georg Agricola (1494-1555) or astronomers and mathematicians like Erasmus Reinhold (1511-1553), nor in major political writings, dedicated to Saxon counts and dukes (and therefore also potential objects of the competitive court environment) as Georg Lauterbecks *Regentbuch* (1556), Christoph Vischers *Bericht aus Gottes Wort* (1573) or Johann Schramms *Fasciculus Historiarum* (1589).

⁵ Even authors like Melchior von Osse, an overall successful and longtime servant to the Saxon princes felt compelled to defend himself, his *Testament* and his expertise. He started his career as council to Duke Georg (1542), later on he worked for Johann Friedrich (of House Ernestine) then from 1548 for Duke Moritz of Saxony (for details about his career in Saxon service cf. Czok, 1987; Kötzschke 1940). It is important to note, however, that many cameralists, as they were highly depending on the mercy of their principal, had to endure prolonged phases of private financial and professional insecurity. The power struggles at court and the intention to persuade the prince of one’s own value form an additional important background of the cameralists’ struggle for credibility (for the fragility of cameralist careers cf. Bauer 1997: 206-217; Smith, 1994).

sovereign would ever be able to get to the very bottom of things again. The space of the “*oikos*” became simply too large. Just large enough however to create the (tragic) figure of the cameralist, who would try to maintain and think in the unity and form of the *oikonomia*, but, just like his prince, was almost doomed to fail in the attempt to simulate the mastery of the whole.

2. Mining and Cameralism

From its beginnings, cameralism has been characterised by a high level of attention to questions of mining and its significance for the country and its people (Springer 2010). The early modern silver mines were, according to Andre Wakefield, central Europe’s great cameralist incubators (Wakefield 2017: 65). Most of the important cameralists like Melchior von Osse, Georg Obrecht, Jakob Bornitz (1560-1625), Johann Joachim Becher, Georg Heinrich Zincke (1692-1769), Johann Heinrich Gottlob von Justi or Joseph Sonnenfels (1732/33-1817) were living and working in German states that were highly depending on this type of industry. Their opinion on mining was hence very approving. Some like Johann Wilhelm Schröder (1640-1688) or Justi, who, like many other cameralists, were themselves active in the field of mining at times, praised the mines as the first, if not the only, certain means to increase the wealth of German lands (Schröder 1752: 111; Justi 1755: 209).

The cameralists’ fascination with mining affairs had two main reasons. Firstly, the natural endowment of central Europe with several remarkable silver deposits - which in turn had a major impact on the monetary system (Wakefield 2017: 61), prompting already the Carolingians to base their currency on silver (Kluge 1999: 82). Secondly, discursive processes from the late middle ages onwards, in particular the fusion of ideas from ancient economics with late medieval myths about hidden underground riches in German lands.

A particularly strong influence on the cameralists of the early modern times had been exerted by the *Politics* of Aristotle, which found its way into the European scholarly discourse amongst others through the Latin translation by Wilhelm von Moerbeke (around 1260) (Söder 2008: 60; Oexle 1992: 535). For Aristotle, mining stood as a *third* element inbetween the necessary and praiseworthy natural acquisition, a living of the fruits of the earth (Aristotle 1980: 1258a 25-37) on the one hand, and the artificial, revenue-based arts such as trade, money transactions and paid labour (1259a 21-28) on the other hand. Mining therefore had a part in both '*natural as well as revenue-based ways of acquisition*' (1258b 27-34). This semantic interposition subsequently put it in an exceptional position both to fit

into the natural order of things and to allow space for an active pursuit of resources. The growth of metals and minerals from the bosom of Mother Earth allowed gain without taking,⁶ i.e. without creating new variants and compounds within the traditional arrangements of world and society. Such sources of wealth, which were able to integrate the traditional normative-conservative framework with the (princely) pursuit of profit, were of the greatest importance to the cameralists. "*Naturalia media*" are, according to Georg Obrecht, all sources which "*cum facto hominis juncta, bear much and great benefit to a regent and overlord*" (Obrecht 1617: 100f.) because they grant him an income without burdening the subjects and hence, social peace.

The hoped-for "*great benefit*" was also due to the fact that the amount of (circulating) money was seen as an increasingly important indicator of political power and territorial prosperity. "*Pecunia nervus rerum*" was an often repeated cameralist mantra (Stolleis 1983), which admittedly made the mining of silver and gold all the more important for reasons of welfare and power politics. Many German territories were well aware that they could not compete with nations such as France, the Netherlands and England when it came to commerce and manufacturing. The mining of precious metals therefore suggested a viable and reliable way of strengthening one's own political position. From the 15th century at the latest, this became all the more true as, e.g. in the form of the *Germania* treatise (1457/58) of Aeneas Silvius Piccolomini (1405-1464), the conviction circulated in the German-speaking regions that the home soil was particularly blessed with ore and mineral wealth. There would be "*rarely a single mountain*", Obrecht argued, "*which does not contain certain metalla*" - a conscientious regent would therefore only have to "*search diligently*" in his lands to find some "*useful metalli fodinae*" (Obrecht 1617: 101). Similar statements can be found in Sebastian Münster's (1488-1552) *Cosmographia* (1544) or the mining books of Georg Agricola (1494-1555). "*Germany*" is, according to the latter, "*more than other territories rich with metals [...]*" (Agricola 1955: 75), one could even "*dare to assert that Germany has more silver than all other countries, even an abundance of it!*" (124) Philipp Wilhelm Hörnigk in particular would later develop and expand this *topos* so vehemently in the case of Austria that the naive reader must have been inclined to believe that he would only need to put a spade in his neighbour's garden in order to come across a considerable amount of precious metal deposits. Even the Viennese forest "*in front of the eyes of the Kayserliche Residenz*", Hörnigk assures the (princely) reader, "*is laden with rich silver ore*" (Hörnigk 1684: 51).

⁶ Also von Justi in the 18th century would still use the term "*bosom of [mother] earth*" ("*Schooße der Erden*") (Justi, 1766: 255).

3. The deep art of mining

The systematic recording and mapping of "*the things hidden underground*"⁷ and the undertaking of a "*complete mountain geography*" (Carl Friedrich Zimmermann) would remain an unfulfilled desideratum until the late 18th and 19th century (Klein 2016: 147). The statements by Obrecht or Hörnigk quoted above were hence highly speculative considering the state of knowledge at the time. Beyond all exaggeration, however, there was a true core to the story of subterranean riches. In fact, the conditions for mining undertakings had been comparably good in German territories. Both the Central German Uplands and parts of the Alps were sprinkled by a large number of metal deposits (Bartels and Klappauf 2012: 164). Although these were often small in size, they were nevertheless enough to spark widespread montanist activities already in the Middle Ages which allowed Emperor Charles V (1500 - 1558) to proudly conclude in 1525 that "*there were more mines...in the Holy Roman Empire and German lands than anywhere else in the whole of Christendom*" (quoted from Suhling 1983: 94).

When Melchior von Osse was born in Ossa (Geithain) in 1506, forty percent of the income of the Kursachsen Rentkammer came from mining and metallurgy. Although this share would fall to about ten percent by 1600, the importance of the mining industry for the prince and Saxony remained outstanding. More than 50,000 fl per annum, not counting the additional profits from princely Kux possessions of approx. 8,000 to 11,000 fl, were still flowing into Dresden's coffers during the two decades after 1582 (Schirmer 2001: 129f.). In addition, a pronounced awareness of the positive effects that a flourishing mining industry could have on the prosperity of a region can be found in the country from early on. The fact that this knowledge was not only a particular insight of a few, but rather a recognised concept within governmental and scholarly circles, is impressively demonstrated by one of the first economic treatises circulating in Germany, the so-called *Gemeine Stymmen Von der Muentze* (publ. 1548 in Leipzig, written around 1530). Our mines, the text concludes, "*have increased the sustenance of people living in these lands/ increased the value of the goods / improved the income of the laudable nobility/ because at places where there is a lot of people/ there is also trade/ there is opportunity for the nobility to profit from their cattle breeding/ and fishponds/ and they can sell grain/ barley/ oat/ for a lot of money [but also] [...] the citizens can serve their beer/ sell cloth/ skirt/ and shoes/ horseshoes/ lock/ ribbon/ [...] knife/ belt / bag [...] and will receive good coins in return. Also*

⁷ In 1752 physician, mineralogist and geologist Johann Gottlob Lehmann (1719-1767) would still have to lament the blatant lack of detailed geological descriptions and illustrations of underground mineral deposits (cf. Lehmann 1752).

the baker and butcher and all other craftsmen will profit while the farmer can tend to his field with much benefit [...]” (3).

The fact that such large numbers of people and trades could become related and dependent on the mining industry was still a relatively new situation at that time. The emergence of mining towns such as the Saxon city of Freiberg, which quickly emerged from the settlement of Christiansdorf after the silver findings of 1168, demonstrated impressively how medieval mining was already able to mobilise crowds of people, but such events were then rather unique in character. Generally, medieval mines were still run by self-employed miners (so-called "Eigenlehner") or by mining cooperatives,⁸ i.e. by small-scale and capital-weak forms of organisations which were merely equipped for near-surface operations (Dietrich 1991: 9; Bogsch 1933: 93). Only simple tools and devices were deployed to dig into the ground until intruding masses of groundwater would eventually render the continuation of works too expensive. Often people would subsequently start a new mine just a few meters away from the old one. Because of that, the degree of professionalisation was correspondingly low until the 13th century. In many regions, the primary occupation was still farming with mining only as a secondary occupation (Stöger 2006: 170).

By the second half of the 14th century at the latest, a point was reached when the majority of easily accessible ores had been exploited in most regions. Combined with repeated plague outbreaks, rising labour costs and difficult (rainy) climatic conditions, this eventually led to a prolonged phase of crisis in Central European silver mining (Bartels and Klappauf 2012: 239ff.). The financial resources of the "Eigenlehner" and cooperatives were simply too small to meet the costs of draining and extraction in greater depths under such circumstances. Even important mining districts such as Freiberg suffered acutely from the lack of financial resources. Freiberg miners complained for example in 1447 that they had no external financial support which would be the reason why "*us poor pitmen have to continue [...] to mine all alone, only helped by some impoverished craftsmen*" by our side (quoted after Wilsdorf 1975: 161, Fn. 12).

A few years before this complaint however, significant innovations in the mining industry had already begun to emerge. The financial requirements of the mines and the growing interest of princes, towns and bourgeoisie in a prosperous mining industry had led to experiments with new types of business organisation. A decisive innovation in this context was the conversion of the hitherto non-commodified

⁸ The pits were divided into parts (later called "Kux") according to the number of miners in the cooperative. These were not only working in the mine, but were also entitled to receive income from the collectively generated surplus or, in bad times, were obliged to pay subsidies to the community fund; (cf. Köhler 1955: 58f.)

cooperative mine shares into freely negotiable and transferable share certificates (Dietrich 1991: 36), so-called *Kux*, which were soon to be traded on the markets of mining cities as well as on important trade fairs in cities such as Leipzig, Frankfurt, Nuremberg or Antwerp (Bogsch 1933: 100; Asmussen 2016: 161). This innovation and the following emergence of the "*capitalist mining cooperation*" (Laube 1974: 83) opened up the mining industry for investments from the ranks of the nobility, the clergy as well as the bourgeoisie.

The effects of this development, starting around 1440 in the Falkensteiner Revier in Tyrol (Suhling 1983: 107), were resounding. The massive inflow of funds soon allowed existing mines to be drained and new mines to be established. Around 1470, when "*finally a mighty ore was found*" (quoted after Kratzsch 1972: 13), the Saxon Erzgebirge became the center of a veritable "*mountain fever*" (Kahleyß 2013: 158). More and more new deposits were discovered, eventually resulting in great numbers of mines all over the district. Rumors and news of fantastic silver findings soon circulated through the Holy Roman Empire and attracted thousands of soldiers of fortune, miners, day laborers, farmers, craftsmen and merchants to the remote and sparsely populated regions of the Erzgebirge. "*As if on a pilgrimage*," the chronicler Petrus Albinus (1543 - 1598) wrote (Bönhoff 1910:11; quoted after Karant-Nunn 1989: 309f.), they streamed into the newly founded settlements. After silver findings near today's Frohnau the town of Annaberg was built within only seven years (1492 - 1499). Already in 1509 Duke Georg would proudly describe Annaberg as "*a beautiful large town*" which "*comprises a great number of over 8000 people*" (Laube 1974: 34). Not far away, the city of Buchholz (1501) emerged on a green meadow. Similarly, deserted villages such as Glashütte (1506) or lost hamlets such as Schlieten, later called Marienberg (1521), turned into prosperous and animated population centres (Dietrich 1991: 23).

Along with these demographic effects (the Saxon Erzgebirge soon counted 50,000 to 70,000 inhabitants) (Schirmer 1997: 130; Straube 1997), which applied similarly to all Middle European districts that entered the capitalist phase of mining at that time, fundamental changes within the daily mining business were introduced. The influx of large amounts of capital allowed the pits to advance into previously unattained depths. While in the 14th century the lack of financial means had still hampered the development and installation of techniques and procedures for water elevation (so-called *Wasserkünste*), this changed in the course of the 15th and 16th century. Technical innovations like the Bulgen-, the Heinzenkunst and finally the so-called Ehrenfriedersdorfer would emerge and eventually allow the water to be pumped up to 30 meters and more (Kraschewski 2012: 288; Blaschke 1967: 163).

One consequence of these processes was, that the mining industry, as Melchior von Osse and cameralists after him would experience it, was not only exceptionally "*capital-committing and cost-*

intensive" (Kaufhold 2000: 70f.) but also extremely complex. In order to reach mining depths of over 270 m as in Schneeberg, a highly differentiated and effective network of various forms of knowledge and professions was required on site (Hoppe 1908: 93; Kraschewski 2012: 251f.) In the meantime, 3000 worked underground in the Annaberg and Marienberg mines and 4000 in Joachimsthal (Laube 1974: 115). Thirty different occupational groups can be identified in the process of silver mining already by the beginning of the 16th century (Westermann 2012: 427). So-called *Bremser, Führer, Gänger, Haspler, Stollhauer, Klauber, Truhenläufer, Steiger, Probierer* and many other professions were mentioned in documents.⁹ The necessary knowledge for many of these occupations required years of practical experience. How do you recognise ore-bearing rock, what has to be taken into account when driving a drift, how do you timber a vertical shaft, how do you use a hammer and iron? Hence, it was not uncommon for young people to start working and learning in mines from the age of twelve (Sieber 1954: 87).

The metaphoric notion of a *deep* space of economy respective (in this case) of the mining industry does not exhaust itself in the mere and rather obvious picture of vertically driven mines. The image of a mine and the iconic tripartite division into day, surface and subterranean domain nevertheless forms a helpful metaphor to understand the concept of *depth* in this context and its role for cameralist thought. Figure 1, centerpiece of the *Annaberger Bergaltar*, an altar created by the late Gothic panel and glass painter Hans Hesse (* before 1497; † after 1539), consecrated 1521, represents one of the most famous depictions of the Erzgebirge mining landscape in the early 16th century. The forests have been cleared to the horizon. Excavated heaps are piling up. New silver veins are mined and material from the existing pits is extracted. A man stamps rocks, another one pushes a wheelbarrow or leads a horse carriage. For a layman who would then visit this area, the impression of great hustle and bustle had to certainly arise. At the same time, it is clear that what is visible to the visitor's eye was only a highly reduced surface of a far more complex reality behind or beneath. In order to illustrate this problem an exemplary pictorial element within Figure 1 shall be selected.

⁹ A hundred years later the ongoing process of specialisation will have created even more professions: *Fahrhauer, Bohrhauer, Einfachhauer, Gesteinshauer, Gedingehauer, Zimmerhauer [...] Ortshauer, Schießhauer, Schrämhauer, Spitzhauer, Stollnhauer, Strebhauer, Strossenhauer, Kerbhauer*" and so forth (cf. Sieber 1954: 87).

Figure 1: Hans Hesse, *Annaberger mountain altar*, middle section (1521). Annaberg

The conical building in the background, marked by a red frame, is a so-called horse capstan, also called "*roß kunst*" at that time. In it, several horses, often in continuous operation, walked in a circle around a wave, pumping goods and mine water into and out of the mine.¹⁰ This technique had become necessary due to the increasing mining depths and probably appeared in the Saxon Erzgebirge for the first time around 1500 (Feldhaus 1914). If one is to believe the mining scholar Georg Agricola, the sight of these large facilities must have been truly impressive for some contemporaries. "*My God! What a giant machine*", Doctor Johannes Naevius, one of the three protagonists in Agricola's first work *Bermannus* (1530), exclaims in astonishment (Agricola 1955: 86). About twenty years later, in

¹⁰ Normally eight, in special cases up to 24 horses were working in one shift (Wilsdorf 1975: 116; Schirmer 2013: 50).

his famous *De Re Metallica* (1556), Agricola will add some highly detailed descriptions and woodcuts of such horse capstans (cf. Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Georg Agricola, *Vom Bergwerck XII Bücher* [...], Basel (1557), CXXX, CXXVIII.

What at first (cf. Fig. 1) may have looked like a large hut covered with wooden shingles, now reveals itself as an interwoven complex of materials, mechanics and practices. The building on the surface resembles, so to speak, the proverbial tip of the iceberg. It symbolises and incorporates decades of condensed knowledge about the guidance and deflection of the axles, the choice of suitable types of wood, the production of ropes and bearings, the manufacture of lubricants and so forth.

Many of the man-made as well as natural surfaces in the early capitalist Erzgebirge were, at least for the eye of the savant, hiding several layers of interlocking or superimposed levels of historically

generated knowledge.¹¹ From the middle of the 15th century the masses striving for riches, but also the widespread fear of losing one's money or life within the mining business, drove not only iron and hammer into the stone but also human subtlety and intellect.¹² In this way, new differences, new beings and things, were constantly introduced into montane matter. In places where a layman would only perceive channels, rocks and buildings, the expert saw variations, types and forms, both with regard to their functional characteristics and their origins (Dym 2011: 5). In the context of the complex mining world, water for example was not merely water - it could indicate ores and minerals, it could break into pits or provide energy via water wheels. The experienced miner knew that it could make a decisive difference to his practice whether the respective water tasted "*sweet, sour, bitter, tart, salty [or] constricting*" (Agricola 1956: 50). Georg Agricola's *Meurerbrief* (1546), one of the first glossaries of mining vocabulary, impressively demonstrates this heightened awareness for the importance of water and its variants. On several pages he lists all kinds of water, distinguishable for example by color (e.g. "*Red water*", "*Green water*", "*Blue water*"), temperature (e.g. "*Ice water*", "*Snow water*") or taste (e.g. "*Salt water*", "*Seawater*", "*Nitrite water*" or "*Alum water*") (13ff.).

The mining language in general can be regarded as a mirror and embodiment of the above described process of differentiation (Piiirainen 1994). This is for instance documented in a steady stream of increasingly comprehensive dictionaries from about 1500 onwards.¹³ In addition to the humanistic interest in collecting and arranging existing word inventories, a clearly dynamic momentum can be observed here over time (Long 1991). New techniques, instruments and professions, as well as increasingly precise names for rocks and minerals (etc.) soon made a strong growth of the montanist vocabulary necessary. While in the appendix of the "*Bergbüchlein*" by Ulrich Rülein von Calw (1518) there were still only a few technical terms, the list of Plateanus, written in 1530 and later added to the "*Bermannus*", already included 76. Agricola would extend this to 125 terms in 1546 for a new edition of this volume. In the already mentioned *Meurerbrief* about 500 designations are defined (Koch 1963: 32).¹⁴ The most important chronicler of the Saxon Erzgebirge, Petrus Albinus, would later complain in his "*Meißnische Land- und Bergchronika*", published in 1590, that the miners have so "*many special*

¹¹ For example, from the beginning of the 16th century silver ores were not sieved with any kind of fabric, but with specially made horsehair cloths, dyed green, which were particularly suitable for filtering and making silver grains visible (cf. Wilsdorf 1975: 116).

¹² It is hence no surprise, that the number of invention protection rights granted in Saxony in the 16th century would reach dimensions that would only be reached again much later in times of the Industrial Revolution (cf. Creutz 1985: 166).

¹³ Early records – especially in the context of legal texts - of a vernacular mining language in Germany however date back to the 12th century (Asrih 2017: 13).

¹⁴ Today the German mining language comprises almost 20,000 keywords, which are recorded in more than 60,000 word combinations (Heilfurth 1995: 42).

ways to talk" about the ores as well as "*their many and strange instruments: which are used in the art of extraction and processing*". It would have been almost impossible for outsiders like him to learn all these terms, also because the words "*with the times / as there are always some/ which improve old innovations/ or create new things/ are changed*" (Albinus 1590: 3).

4. The deep government

Everyone interested in mining from the early 16th century had to learn that underneath supposedly simple surfaces lay in fact deep reaching systems of differences. This fact, which has both ontological and epistemological consequences, will, as is going to be discussed in detail in the next chapter, become of particular importance for the cameralists. Exploring the *ortu et causis sub rerum*, descending into the manifold worlds below the economic surfaces overloaded both their capabilities and resources as well as the limited space of the written book. In order for these limitations, however, to regularly culminate in a crisis of credibility and legitimacy, a second element was required, which is to be addressed here very briefly; a process that unfolded almost complementarily to the growing complexity of economic realities: *the emergence of an increasingly comprehensive governmental apparatus*.

Of course, this process was not limited to mining districts alone. Rather, one could observe a build-up of bureaucracies throughout the Holy Roman Empire from about the late 15th century onwards (Jeserich et al. 1983). The growth of the cities, the economy, of crafts and commerce at the time led to increasingly dynamic social conditions, which could no longer be controlled by traditional, small-scale administrative institutions (Simon 1997: 1209). Important mining districts, however, fulfilled these prerequisites for the emergence of early modern civil service structures *par excellence*, as they formed extremely vibrant and translocally integrated regions. Important voices within the German mining discourse, such as Adolf Laube or Uwe Schirmer, hence argued that the economic conditions of the Saxon Erzgebirge led to the establishment of an administrative structure that was extraordinarily dense and differentiated according to the standards of the time (Schirmer 2009; Laube 1974: 8f.; Neumann 2019).

After the first large silver finds in Freiberg in the 12th century, it soon became clear that neutral authorities were needed to maintain order, settle conflicts within the mining community, distribute mining rights, collect fees and tithes, prevent overworking or initiate and administer the built of

drainage adits (Groß 1990: 34). Initially, these tasks laid in the hands of the Freiberg City Council under the supervision of a margravian commissioner (Bartels and Fessner 2012: 478). At the beginning of the 14th century, the so-called *Freiberger Bergrecht A*, a first fragmentary compilation of customary montane-rights, would already list a few supplementary offices. In addition to the "*bergmeister*" (surveyor of the mines) and a "*lyer*" who assisted him, a "*bergrichtere*" (judge for mining affairs), as well as "gesworne lute" (mountain jurors) and the "*czendenere*" (collector of the tithe) are mentioned here (Ermisch 1887).

The position of the *Bergmeister* integrated large parts of the administrative tasks within one post. He was responsible for the overall supervision of the entire mining operation. Among other things, he visited new quarries and pits, granted and measured fiefdoms, withdrew and confirmed mining rights and officially represented the interests of the sovereign in the mining district. In May 1328 Margrave Friedrich of Meißen (1310-1349) issued a comprehensive set of mining regulations which laid down in detail the rights and duties of the *Bergmeister* and his subordinates for all mining districts within the Wettin territory (Bartels and Fessner: 478). Besides this effort, no major additional activity to strengthen and refine the mining administration took place during the 14th century. The release of the revised *Freiberger Bergrecht B* around the middle of the century indicates that there had been an ongoing debate concerning the existing legal framework, the orally handed down customary mining laws etc. (Asrih 2017: 95f.). These discussions however had only led to minor changes concerning the number and functions of mining officials in the region.

The early capitalist developments in the 15th century, however, would fundamentally change the situation. The inflowing masses of workers and capital, the spatial expansion and intensification of (economic) relations, and the growing desire of the sovereign to increase his wealth now almost "*inevitably*" (Groß 1990: 35) led to a growth spurt in the mining administration. In 1466, the Wettin Dukes Ernst and Albrecht established a second mining office (*Bergamt*) for all mines outside Freiberg, Geyer and Ehrenfriedersdorf. Only a few years later it was clear that these additional offices did not suffice to deal with the task of regulating the mining activities in the Erzgebirge. In 1477 a third mining office was therefore established in Schneeberg, in 1500 a fourth one in Annaberg and eventually in 1521 a fifth in Marienberg.

Alongside this, the offices were equipped with more and more personnel. Already the *Freiberger Bergrecht B* had added a *Messer* (surveyor) and a *Oberbergmeister* to the existing yet small list of officials. Now *Oberbergmeister* and *Bergmeister* were supported by a supplementary *Unterbergmeister* (adjunct surveyor of the mines), a mining clerk and additional assistants. The

following *Annaberger Bergordnung* of 1509, "which will for centuries, directly or indirectly and far beyond Saxony's borders, remain a foundation of mining legislation to come" (Ermisch 1987: VII), went even further: A new position was introduced, the so-called *Berghauptmann*, now head of the *Bergamt* (mining office), who would also serve as the representative of the sovereign in the region. He was assigned a *Bergmeister* (surveyor of the mines), eight mountain jurors, twelve collectors of tithe, two *Hüttenreiter* (administering smelting works), a so-called *Ausleiher* (lender), a *Gegenschreiber* (clerk for mine shares) and a *Bergschreiber* (mountain clerk) (Groß 1990: 35). In addition to this, there were *Markscheider* (surveyors), a "*Bergwardein*" (sampler) and supplementary clerks.

These depicted transformations, however, merely outline the developments at the lower administrative level. By the beginning of the 16th century, a growing need was emerging to establish a new powerful intermediate institution, which would not only oversee all montane processes in the country, but could also act as a court of appeal in any kind of legal disputes within this industry. This led in August 1547 to the establishment of the *Oberbergamt* in Freiberg, which was from now on responsible for all matters concerning mining and metallurgy in the Erzgebirge district. The *Oberhauptmann*, who headed this institution, had not only the large task of supervising mining regulations, but also to uncover and remedy grievances within districts, staff offices, visits pits and check bookkeeping practices on site (35f.).

Eventually, even a third bureaucratic layer was needed. In March 1556 Elector August established the position of a chamber council and chamber secretary as a reaction to the growing number of economic issues with which the Wettin court found itself confronted. The first incumbent, Hans von Ponickau, was assigned a wide remit, ranging from princely forests and domains to the handling of gifts and the remuneration of civil servants. In addition, his secretary was already explicitly entrusted "*with the handling of mining affairs*" (Haug 1897: 163). This process marked the beginning of a supreme administrative level for mining matters, based on the now tripartite system of local mining offices and the superior Freiburger *Oberbergamt* as central authority. Here too, an increasingly complex and differentiated institution would eventually emerge. An important step in this context was, among others, the creation of the "*Bergexpedition*" (mountain expedition) by Christian II in 1606. This administrative unit was to serve as a steering and advisory committee for mining matters at the Dresden court, consisting of five members plus an additional secretary and a clerk, equipped with their own premises separate from the old chamber (170f.).

Figure 3: Valentin Noh, *Cover of the Antiphonale from Kutná Hora* (ca 1471), Prague (Czech National Library)

As in the previous chapter, the *depth* of government can best be illustrated by using iconic material from the particular period and region (cf. Fig. 3). When the well-known Czech illuminator Valentin Noh from Jindřichův Hradec finished the title page of the Kutná Hora *Antiphonal* around 1471, Kutná Hora was just about to experience major changes within its mining administration. Analogous to the Saxon Erzgebirge, this mining district had entered a phase of capitalist-entrepreneurial dynamics, soon followed by strong legal-administrative reforms from the late 15th century onwards. In particular the 1486 ordinances of king Wladislaw II. Jagiellone (1456-1516), repeated in 1494, would eventually herald a phase in the course of which the local mining industry gradually came under the control of an increasingly comprehensive sovereign bureaucratic apparatus (Matejková 2011: 208, 219).

The pictorial layout of the *Antiphonal*, which was created just before these major transformations, was still strongly informed by medieval mining realities. It is characterised by a hierarchical structure in which the magistracy at the top finds itself unambiguously distinguished from the lower realm of economic activity and daily life. A banner next to the nobly dressed patricians, including Lord Nicholas, the mine master (from 1470 to 1488) of these days, informs the viewer that " [t]ot' gsu Starssii nad hawerzi" ("these are the supervisors of the miners") (Graham 2000: 322). They populate only a narrow space, which seems to float above all 'lower' temporal things. This pictorial arrangement, in particular the separation of the higher echelons of society on the one hand, and the world of commerce and industry on the other hand, is rather typical for medieval art. There is some evidence, however, that this illustration not only mirrors aesthetical conventions of an era but that it might also be connected to the local context: a small detail in which the symbolic order finds itself disturbed by realistic elements from the Kutná Hora region. From the upper right hand side, miners¹⁵ are pushing into the picture in order to receive orders and instructions. This transgression subverts the symbolic separation of the political and economic space. While only twenty years later the famous illuminator Matthew (Mathaeus) would create (for example in the *Kutná Hora Kanzional*) illustrations in which the realm of the authorities and the mining industry were thoroughly and inseparably blended (Matejková 2011; Fritzsich 1960; Frimmel 1887), Valentin Noh left it to the miners community to bridge the divide between government and economy.

This constellation would change radically in the years after the completion of the *Antiphon*. As was shown by the development of the Erzgebirge mining and administrative system from around 1470 onwards, the government followed the economic processes into their increasingly *deep* (behind or underneath seemingly simple surfaces) space of complexity. Additional levels of administration, new offices and functions were created and large numbers of personnel were hired. From the 16th century onwards, the distance between the upper echelons of the country and the subterranean treasures would be incrementally interspersed with more and more mining officials (Oberbergmeister, Bergmeister, Zehntner and Zehntschreiber, Berggeschworene, Bergschreiber, Gegenschreiber, Schichtmeister, Steiger, Markscheider, Probierer and Austeiler, amongst others). If one studies some of the woodcuts by the aforementioned Georg Agricola with this context in mind, one can see how bureaucracy had become an integral part of the mining scenery. If we return to the metaphoric dimension of the *Antiphonary*, the here depicted miners no longer had to take the symbolic path to the magistracy themselves. The prince or his deputies were now already on site, they were part of the economy -

¹⁵ „Giny pany hawerzy“ (other mining gentlemen).

whether above ground during the inspection of new repositories (Fig. 4, left) or underground, here during the inspection of the technical apparatus below a horse capstan.

Figure 4: Georg Agricola, *Vom Bergwerck XII Bücher [...]*, Basel (1575), XXXI, CLVIII.

5. The shallow realm of the book

It was only in the course of the 18th and 19th century that state and economy emerged as independent spheres and objects within the sciences (Burkhardt 1990: 169ff.). For most cameralists until then however, these fields had been opaque, full of dark areas whose secrets had yet to be explored; spheres of hidden connections and laws, of possible riches as well as dangers. For cameralist authors such as Johann Wilhelm von Schröder (1640-1688) neither the economic nor the political body were transparent territories that could easily be overlooked, traversed or surveyed. They had to be defined in the first place by, for example, exploring and determining which phenomena could and should be regarded as relevant for a specific problem, what senses, instruments and media to use and so forth. Proposals such as those by Schröder's *Staatsbrille* (a system of inventories of all trades in the country)

should accordingly throw "*a political fiat lux*" into this "*chaos confusum*" of the *estates* and their economy, thereby allowing to bring a "*little order*" into these "*masses of people and different trades*" (Schröder 1752: 49, 56; Keller 2016: 363).

A major task for early modern political and economic thinkers was therefore 'learning to see' all the deep differences that the capitalist energies, among others, had inscribed into the order of people and things. Especially in the 17th century, more and more concepts and instruments would appear which were designed to penetrate these confused spaces in order to make them a transparent object for the ambitions of scientists and rulers (Keller 2016: 356). However, no human life, neither that of the prince nor that of the cameralist would have been sufficient to explore and measure the deep economic spaces of things, beings, practices and forms of knowledge, which in the Early Modern Age increasingly unfolded behind the manifold surfaces. These subterranean dimensions were innovative and confusing in ways that already the experts of the 16th century repeatedly pointed to the limits of their knowledge and the limited possibilities of literary representation.¹⁶ According to Georg Agricola, everyone should realize "*how widespread the mining industry is [and] how many sciences and knowledge a miner needs*" to succeed (Agricola 1977: XIII). Whoever wants to be successful within this business must not only know "*which mountain or hill, which place in the valley or fields might be worth exploring*", he must also know about "*the ore veins, the fissures and the faults of the rock*", how the "*work underground is to be accomplished*" and with what means "*all kinds of substances [...] can be tested and prepared for melting [...]*". In addition, he must be well versed in philosophy, medicine, astronomy, arithmetic, the art of building, surveying and drawing as well as in law (1f.). It seems that the more unexplored and messier these underground worlds appeared to their contemporaries, the more they tended to define all thinkable dimensions of (scientific) knowledge as possibly relevant to the subject. It is not surprising then, that the limits of literary translation and representation of certain crafts or trades formed a recurring subject in the scholarly discourse of these days. Ultimately, "*no book could be written in this world [...] which would contain [all] the [mining] skills*" and matters. Therefore everyone interested in mining would have to eventually "*go into the pits*" by themselves to talk to experienced pitmen and to learn by participating in the daily life of mining (Soleas 1600: 14).

This situation was problematic for the cameralists in several respects. In comparison to their scientific successors, they were still very much bound to a Unitarian concept of state and household. The medieval ideal of a personalised rule, of a patriarch representing and overseeing every detail, every

¹⁶ The failure of the written word comes through in many attempts to describe artisanal understanding (cf. Smith 2004: 81; Kemp 1977).

event in his territory, guided and inspired their works.¹⁷ In the context of a governmental reality that proved to be increasingly complex, they were all the more involved in an effort to create and maintain the contrary image of its identity. Their leading metaphor of *house* and *household* formed a mirror for this type of pursuit. These terms suggested that there existed a manageable realm of knowledge. This illusion in turn formed the foundation of their profession. They were hired upon the promise that they would condense all necessary information concerning the princely *oikonomia* into the unity of the book, thereby providing their mentor with the means to cultivate at least the image of an omnipotent sovereign.

This task of course was almost impossible to resolve. When already specialists of individual trades referred to their limited possibilities to penetrate the subtleties of their subject and to translate them into writing - how then could one possibly expect to succeed in understanding the underlying principles of the whole princely economy? Johann Coler (1566-1639), paragon and first major author of the German so-called 'household literature' (*Hausväterliteratur*), characterises in his *Oeconomia Oder Haußbuch* (1593) the science of managing (large) households as such a "*complex art*" that „no one could, even in the span of a lifetime, learn all about it" (Coler 1593: 1).¹⁸ It is important to note, however, that the thematic scope of the household literature was still rather small in comparison with cameralist books. While the former could focus on agricultural issues, the latter found themselves (theoretically) confronted with the whole cosmos of territorial trades and crafts. From the administration of dominions¹⁹ to mining and smelting works, from the management of government to commerce and the establishment of early manufactories – already the economy of Elector August in 16th century Saxony had reached levels of complexity that could not possibly, not even remotely, be translated into a book or understood by a single individual like Melchior von Osse. August, an entrepreneurial spirit himself, opened up different sectors of the economy (for example smelting, charcoal burning, cloth production or even the development of waterways) for private money, knowledge and initiative (Falke 1868). His incessant search for experts along with documents like Heinrich Cramer von Claußbruch's 1587 memorandum²⁰ on the establishment of cloth-workshops in Saxony strongly emphasize the growing complexity within the princely *oikonomia*.

¹⁷ For the longevity of the normative idea of personalized rule see for example Volkmar 2008.

¹⁸ This claim will be repeated by others following in his wake, for example by Franz Philipp Florinus (1649-1699) in his *Oeconomus Prvdens Et Legalis* (1702).

¹⁹ Agricultural literature like the 16th century treatise of Abraham von Thumbshirn impressively illustrates the complexity of managing large agrarian dominions in Saxony (cf. Thumbshirn 1616).

²⁰ Edited in Werner 1971: p.80ff.

Because of all this, cameralists were almost inevitably confronted with the danger of being accused of naivety, ignorance or even fraud. This is all the more true since they had to reckon with possible opponents in the court environment as their proposals would not only be potentially read by 'real' practitioners in an advisory position but also by increasingly specialised civil servants. Protecting one's own credibility therefore meant for the cameralist to walk that thin and fragile line between the deep space of economy and the deep space of government. The Saxon mountain administration, this long chain of officials that linked the Dresden cabinets with the pitmen in the Erzgebirge mines, not only became a powerful and complex institution following the end of the 15th century (an institution which became extremely difficult to reform even for insiders like Friedrich Anton von Heynitz (1725-1802)) (Wakefield 2009: 34). Their bureaucrats also had enough subject-specific knowledge to refute or even expose consultants or cameralists that were intervening with their affairs.

A typical example in this context are the complaints of Johann Heinrich Gottlob von Justi, who would write that the "*Bergverstaendigen*" he spoke to reacted skeptically or even dismissive to his 'excellent' suggestions for the mining industry (Justi 1755: 217). According to von Justi, such stubborn conservative persons and '*envious obstructors*' would block any progress in mining and mining administration (222). On closer inspection however, an attitude like this could not come as a surprise - not only because bureaucratic apparatuses might be potentially inclined to react conservatively, but also because von Justi made it all too easy for mining experts to ridicule his impulses and publicly denounce them. He expressed for example high demands concerning the amount of knowledge required in mining, sharply condemning the bad state of contemporary mining science, in which "*no high level [...] has yet been reached*" (220). After this introduction however, he proceeded with merely a handful of pages in which he presented a "*first outline [...] and [...] instruction, concerning all [sic; A.L.] the [mining] objects that [one] must get to know*" (Justi 1766: 268f.); only a few lines of von Justi had to suffice to cover issues which were complex enough to fill several books already in the 16th century. Consequently, the denunciation of such naïve cameralist interventions must certainly have been easy for any person that was as experienced in mining affairs as a mining official.

6. An (im)possible science of things

There is something tragic about the cameralist profession. It was supposed to give practical (hence rather easy to falsify) advice for the management of the princely household - it should report from the

depths of economy and state while constantly risking success and credibility by taking on an unfulfillable task. A good sovereign and *paterfamilias* knows about "every opportunity within his country and government", a mantra that would often be repeated by the economic literature of the early modern period, for this was considered the best way for him to stimulate and use all its treasures and potentials. The cameralists not only emphasised "*that the eye of the master makes the horse fat*" (cp. Fig.5),²¹ they also promised that their services could be a pure and transparent medium, able to bridge the growing gap between the princes' eye and his object(s).

The Saxon cameralist Melchior von Osse shows an impressive intuition concerning the dangers that came along with the interplay of deep economy and government on the one hand, as well as the limited possibilities of book and man on the other. He knew that even the most "godly, wise, understanding, [and] pious" sovereign needed officials (also "in [the] mines") who would "instead of the lord himself listen to the people, decide, protect, handle, sanction the wrong-doers, make and defend good order" (Osse 1717: 159). Nevertheless, through long years in Saxon service he anticipated that many of these officials would intrigue against him and his proposals. A prince is always surrounded by 'hypocrites' who "caress" him, who "support his volitions and lust and all [his] disorderly inclinations and desires [...]" (147) and "diligently tell the Lord only what he likes to hear, so that they may attain mercy and favour" (179). Therefore, even valid and well-informed arguments from the depths of administration and business had to reckon with hostile voices by, in the case of Saxon mining at that time, persons such as Merten Planer, Michel Schönleben or Simon Bogner (Neumann 2019: 327ff.). These highly ambitious mining officials with excellent connections to Elector August would probably not have hesitated a second to discredit any unqualified or unpleasant advice from von Osse.

²¹ A proverb that can be traced back to Xenophon. In his "Oikonomikos" he wrote about a barbarian king who once "received a noble horse" and hence "asked one of the most recognised horse breeders" about the most important means to nourish and breed such a horse. The answer he received was: "the eye of the Master" (cf. Meyer 1975: 58).

Figure 5: Jacob Jordaens, *The eye of the master makes the horse fat* (17th century),
Galery Alte Meister/ Wilhelmshöhe Castle.

Von Osse would navigate these shoals extraordinarily carefully. At first, he suggested that he was told of the corruption of civil servants within the mining districts. "*Partisan [...], [and] selfish regiments*" would deceive the "*poor[...] people*" and miners and thus bring numerous mines "*into massive decline*". But instead of proposing concrete suggestions for a better management of the mining process, he simply tried to convince the prince himself to penetrate into the depths of the economic and administrative space. It is of the utmost importance "*that the Lord takes personal care of the mines*", von Osse insisted. Additionally, the appointment of the "*mining-offices with honest, pious, understanding people*" is, according to von Osse, necessary in order for the sovereign himself to develop a "great understanding" concerning the mining processes and everything that is "*attached to the same*". To this end, he should visit the districts as often as possible, "*spend many days at the same places*", experience and inquire about all things himself, use pit foremen and hewer as informants, and thus examine everything and everyone. This would eventually create such respect among all "*officers, miners and other mountain people [...]* that they would come to think that nothing could happen at the mines without Your Grace knowing" (93f.).

Either the cameralist had to bring the master to the horse or the horse to the master. While maintaining the unity of the house, the aim was to bridge the distance of knowledge and power between the prince

and his objects – everything else would mean risking that the "good field" might be spoiled by "thistles and thorns" (163). Of course, most cameralists would not act as carefully as von Osse did. Many set out to penetrate the depths of the still unadjusted economic and political-administrative spheres, aiming to return to their noble clients with hidden treasures of practical knowledge from these underground worlds.

A typical example for this type of cameralist would be Johann Joachim Becher. In his major cameralist work, the *Political Discourse* (1668), he would elaborate among others on the subtleties of silk manufacture, the care of mulberry trees and the "juice of the silk-worm" (Becher 1668: 40), the cultivation of "hemp and flax" (82), the book trade, the production of high-quality glass and the processing of diverse metals. He would dive briefly into the complexities of a trade, present a series of data and advices, just in order to quickly resurface and continue with another topic - sometimes accompanied by a short hint "why the author didn't go into more detail" (101) and left out many "specialiora" (103). He would assure his audience that if only the circumstances were different he could easily "report and explain all the prices of goods/ as they run at the moment/ all indicators of their quality/ their variants/ terms [...] and all the skills of the craftsmen and merchants underneath them" (101f.) – but which expert could possibly believe him here? Undoubtedly one did not have to "be a merchant/ [...] [to] understand the art of commerce". Nevertheless, the example of early modern mining firmly underlines that "great journeys" and the direct contact with various trades, "their work/termini and instruments" (Preface) were at best suitable for scratching the surfaces of the economic depths.

From the late 18th century on things would change. Cameralism became a university subject soon to be replaced by an array of specialised disciplines. Alongside the critique and demise of the "imperium paternale" (Immanuel Kant) (Kant 1965) came governmental and scientific realities that superseded traditional "household" semantics by differentiated and specialised economic discourses which no longer needed to cultivate the (illusion of the) unity of book, prince and territory (Richarz 1991: 167). It is the rule, the knowledge, the economics of the many, which then substituted old Unitarian ideals. Additionally (or furthermore), the epistemology and ontology of economics would adapt to realities that had overstrained cameralist practice for centuries. Economic science would increasingly begin to bundle the newly emerged deep space of economy and separate it from its own practice as a sphere with its own logical structure. While the "good" cameralist was still trying to descend into the subtleties of the trades, the "good" economist now had to learn and understand the ocean of things, people, passions and knowledge, subsumed under the term "economy", only by reading and interpreting the movement of the waves, the patterns on the surface. Since one suspected that it was almost impossible

to "unveil" the underlying "rationality and concatenation", the "objective foundations" behind and underneath economic events, one inevitably switched from substances to phenomena, from essences to laws, from beings to their regularities (Foucault 2012: 302). Becher and his colleagues, however, still had to "take the bait/ and continue/ until one comes into the depth" (Becher 1668: 114) - this pursuit symbolised both the prerequisite of their success as well as the danger and inescapable tragedy of their trade.

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